

Measuring the Chromatic Effect of Atmospheric
Point-Spread-Function in Optical Wavelength
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1 Abstract

One of the next generation of sky survey telescopes, the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST), is going to be built in 2019. In order to achieve better precision in measuring the cosmic shear by the weak lensing effect, several systematic biases need to be precisely fixed. One of the biases originates from the dependence of the atmospheric Point Spread Function (PSF) on wavelength. PSF describes how light is smeared by the atmosphere, resulting in the occurrence of the twinkling starlight, and its chromatic effect complicates its correction. In this project, we attempt to measure the dependence of PSF on wavelength by utilizing the Parallel Imager for Southern Cosmological Observation (PISCO) data and comparing the results with the previous simulation and theoretical prediction.

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2 Introduction

2.1 Observing the Cosmic Shear through Weak Gravitational Lensing Effect

The latest research shows that we are living in a flat, acceleratedly expanding universe where we can only observe 5% of the matter. Other than the ordinary matter, 27% of the universe consists of dark matter and 68% dark energy.

Figure 1: Demonstration of how gravitation lensing of a cluster bends the light from the background source (Credit: Tony Tyson, Greg Kochanski and Ian Dell'Antonio; Frank O'Connell and Jim McManus, adopted from The New York Times)[5]

The nature of dark matter has been one of the most compelling topics of modern cosmology. Dark matter plays a decisive role in the formation of galaxies and

clusters, as well as the large structure of the universe. The only known way of interaction between dark matter and normal matter is by gravitational force. Thus, measuring the gravitational interaction is one of the keys to understanding the nature of dark matter and its role in forming the observable universe. There are two types of gravitational lensing effect, the strong lensing effect and the weak lensing effect. We usually study the strong lensing effect case by case and study the weak lensing effect through statistical approaches. By definition, the strong lensing effect usually distorts the shape of a galaxy by over 25%. A typical interaction that causes the strong lensing effect is galaxy-cluster interaction, shown in Figure 1. On the other hand, a low density of mass can only cause the weak lensing effect. To observe the weak lensing effect, we need large amounts of data to average out the noises.

If the weak lensing effect is so hard to observe, why are we interested in it? One of the most important reasons is that the weak lensing effect is useful for us to reveal the large structure of the universe. When the light from a distant galaxy passes through the large structure of the universe, the weak lensing effect causes a shear called cosmic shear on the shape of the galaxy. However, cosmic shear is very hard to observe; the distortion it causes on the background galaxy is about 0.1% to 1% [9].

Since every galaxy has its own shape, and the cosmic shear on the galaxy is insignificant compared to its intrinsic shape, we need to average the shape of numerous galaxies to observe any cosmic shear on these galaxies, shown in Figure 2. By measuring the shape of millions or even billions of galaxies, the statistical error of the overall shape calculated from the dataset will be small enough for us to see the cosmic shearing effect caused by the weak gravitational lensing effect of the large structure. Several new generations of sky surveys are trying to get more precise weak lensing effect measurements including the Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST) that will be built in 2019 in Chile.

2.2 The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope (LSST)

The Large Synoptic Survey Telescope is one of the most powerful next-generation survey telescopes, with an 8.4-meter main mirror [8]. There are several features that make LSST a unique survey telescope.

First, the LSST has a large field of view that can cover 49 times the area of the moon. The wide view enables LSST to observe billions of objects at the same time, and go through the whole observable sky in three days. The synoptic survey that

Figure 2: We can not separate the cosmic shear from the intrinsic shape of individual galaxies, however, by taking the average of their shapes and observe the overall shape, we will be able to see the subtle shear from the large structure. If there is no shear at all (first row), we should expect an isotropic overall shape. If the overall shape is not isotropic (second row), it indicates that there is some cosmic shear exerted on these galaxies.

the LSST conducts can provide researchers with a massive dataset of a "dynamic universe".

Second, the LSST is going to generate the largest public data set in the world by continuously observing the sky for 10 years. It will produce tens of petabytes of data, making lots of scientific goals ranging from the solar system to cosmology accomplishable. The large amount of data will also give rise to novel data analysis techniques. Most importantly, the numerous sets of data are crucial for statistical approaches toward cosmic shear measurement.

Since the dataset of LSST is so large, the statistical uncertainty of the shear effect of the galaxy that the LSST can measure will be less than 1% [1]. As Figure 3 shows, when the dataset expands and the equivalent brightness of the measurement

Figure 3: Noise from measuring the ellipticity vs. observational brightness of a galaxy. The shaded area is where counting statistics dominate. But when the object gets brighter, the atmospheric distortion error (ATM), the tracking error (TR), and wavefront correction error (WV) become dominant [7]. (Credit: Chihway Chang)

increases, the stochastic uncertainty of the shear measurement will be dominated by systematics[7]. One of the most significant systematics is caused by atmospheric distortion. Other systematic uncertainties include the CCD effect and other chromatic biases of the telescope. In this project, we will be focusing on the systematic association with the atmospheric effect.

When the light from a star goes through a turbulent atmosphere, the non-uniform density of air will twist the light, making it move constantly. After a long exposure, a point source will become a light disk. The probability density of that disk is called the Point-Spread-Function (PSF) shown in Figure 4. PSF is the cause of "atmosphere seeing" [3], which describes how "sharp" an observational environment is.

PSF is chromatic and therefore behaves differently with different wavelengths. However, chromatic Point-Spread-Function is one of the biggest issues that distort the shape of galaxies for ground-based telescopes[1], which later causes a systematic error in measuring the weak gravitational lensing effect. After the dispersion by the PSF, the roundness of a galaxy increases, while the ellipticity of the galaxy decreases. (Figure 5). A common way to obtain the true shape of the galaxy is to

Figure 4: At first sight, the star looks like a spotted pattern, after a while, it becomes a blurry disk [15] (Credit: Andreas Quirrenbach)

deconvolve the observed galaxy with a chromatic PSF kernel. To acquire a chromatic PSF kernel, one needs to measure the real-time PSF of the exposure from a star, and calculate the chromatic effect. Thus, measuring the chromatic effect precisely is important for correcting the systematics caused by atmosphere turbulence.

Figure 5: This image demonstrates how an oval galaxy’s roundness increases when convolved with a round PSF [6] (Credit:Jiwon Park)

When we measure the shape of galaxies on a ground-based telescope, the galaxies are all affected by the real-time PSF. To get rid of the PSF and measure the true shape of the galaxy, we need to deconvolve the galaxy with the PSF measured from the star close to the galaxy. However, the PSF measured from the stars around the galaxy is different from the PSF for the galaxy, since the PSF is chromatic, and galaxies and stars usually have very different Spectrum of Energy Distributions (SEDs). The difference in SEDs between the galaxies and sample stars and our limited knowledge of chromatic PSF is the cause of the systematic error from the

atmosphere. For example, if we want to measure a galaxy with lots of star formation, which means its spectrum will be blue, and there is a red giant nearby, the PSF measured by the red giant will be smaller than the real PSF for the galaxy.

As a result, we must know how PSF relates with wavelength so that we can derive the chromatic PSF from a specific object, and use it as the deconvolution kernel for all bands. By knowing the wavelength dependence of PSF and measuring the real-time PSF for a star with a specific wavelength, we can fully reconstruct the chromatic PSF for exposure.

A relatively generic model of predicting chromatic PSF is derived from the Kolmogorov model developed by Andrey Kolmogorov in the mid-20th century. Assuming the instantaneous PSF $I(x, y)$ and the phase power spectrum $P(\vec{k})$ [12][13] in it is given by,

$$I(x, y) \propto |\mathcal{F}[P(\vec{k})e^{\frac{-2\pi i}{\lambda}W(\vec{k})}]|^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\Phi(\kappa) = \frac{0.033}{0.423k^2Z} r_0^{\frac{5}{3}} \kappa^{-\frac{11}{3}} \quad (2)$$

where the r_0 is the Fried parameter, κ is the spatial frequency of the turbulence, and k is the wave number $2\pi/\lambda$, the wavelength dependence of the Full-Width Half Maximum (FWHM) on angle resolution for PSF in Kolmogorov model is described as:

$$FWHM(\lambda) = a\lambda^{-\frac{1}{5}} \quad (3)$$

where a is the scale constant that fluctuate over time.

However, the commonly used PSF kernel derived from the Kolmogorov model, based on the turbulence model that $PSF \propto \lambda^{-\frac{1}{5}}$, is not precise enough in predicting the wavelength dependence of PSF required by LSST and Dark Energy Survey (DES) [1]. The deviation of the model from the true PSF becomes significant when the galaxy survey contains numerous galaxies such that the statistic error gets lower than the systematic error caused by chromatic PSF. We need a more precise model to determine the wavelength dependence of the chromatic PSF. Assume the power index on the wavelength is p (we are going to call it power factor p), and

$$FWHM(\lambda) = a\lambda^p \quad (4)$$

where a is a constant. To get a more precise prediction of the chromatic PSF, the Dark Energy Science Collaboration simulated the PSF kernel by utilizing the Von Karman model to calculate the chromatic effect of the atmosphere. The Von Karman model is modified from the Kolmogorov model and provides us with a better prediction for the wavelength dependence of FWHM by adding a scale length L_0 to the phase power spectrum of the turbulence model[12][13]

$$\Phi(\kappa) = \frac{0.033}{0.423k^2Z} r_0^{\frac{5}{3}} (\kappa^2 + (\frac{2\pi}{L_0})^2)^{-\frac{11}{6}} \quad (5)$$

where the outer scale L_0 is added to equation 3. The outer scale is the outer length of the eddies in the turbulent atmosphere [12]. And Kolmogorov model is a special case of the Von Karman model assuming the outer scale is infinity, that is, there are no separate eddies in the atmosphere. In a real atmosphere, eddies are at the length of the outer scale when they are just created, and will cascade down into smaller and smaller eddies with time. Theoretical calculation and simulation based on the Von Karman model show that under different circumstances of the outer scale, the wavelength power p changes according to the diagram in the upper part of Figure 6. We also find a second theoretical calculation of the relationship between chromatic PSF vs. outer scale, shown in the lower part of Figure 6. Two calculations show that the smaller the outer scale is, the smaller the power factor p is. But they are not in agreement on the value of p .

Additionally, p is not only a function of outer scale, but also of wavelength. According to Park's simulation, p changes linearly with the wavelength. It also shows that the change in p over the observation wavelength of LSST is less than 0.02, and this is within the accepted uncertainty for p [4]. So, we can regard p as a constant over different wavelengths in our measurement while still fulfilling the requirement of LSST.

If we have the precise chromatic PSF model as the Von Karman model predicts, we will be able to measure the full PSF information with one star. To measure the Full-Width of Half-Maximum $FWHM_i$ on some filter i with efficiency $e_i(\lambda)$ for a star with SED $S(\lambda)$, the FWHM of the PSF is $a\lambda^p$ and since we know p , the FWHM of i band is given by

$$FWHM_i = \int aS(\lambda)e_i(\lambda)\lambda^p \quad (6)$$

By measuring $FWHM_i$ in the exposure, we can easily calculate a and fully understand the wavelength dependence of FWHM as $a\lambda^p$, assuming that the power

Figure 6: **Up:** Simulation of power factor p under different outer scale lengths [6] (Credit: Park) **Down:** Theoretical prediction of the relationship between the outer scale and power factor p [2] (Credit: Gulshen Gulshen)

factor p stays relatively constant over different wavelengths.

In this paper, we are going to measure the chromatic PSF using the data from the Parallel Imagery of Southern Cosmological Observation (PISCO). Since PISCO is 85 miles away from the site of LSST, and they also have similar observation wavelengths, the result of our measurement can provide the LSST's galaxy survey with a reasonable suggestion on predicting the chromatic PSF. The outer scale length on the site of LSST is about 30 meters [10], which means the p factor is going to be around -0.25 according to Park's simulation[6] and will be -0.32 according to Gulshen's calculation[2]. No matter which outer scale is correct, the measurement of the wavelength dependence of chromatic PSF will help LSST correct the bias caused by deconvolving the PSF.

3 Instrumentation

Because of the fact that atmosphere seeing fluctuates all the time (Figure 7), we can not properly measure the wavelength dependence of PSF using normal telescopes since they take images of a star field one band at a time. The fluctuation will wash over the differences in the PSFs.

Figure 7: PSF of four bands of PISCO, we can see that atmosphere fluctuate all the time, but chromatic effect stays the same for all bands

In this project, we use a novel instrument called the Parallel Imagery for Southern Cosmology Observations(PISCO). PISCO is installed on the 6.5 meter Magellan Telescope located at Las Campanas Observatory[16]. PISCO is unique for the scientific goal of this project for two reasons.

First, PISCO has a unique optics design of the instrument, shown in Figure 8. After the light is collected by the Magellan Telescope, the signal is split into 4 channels with 3 dichroic cubes. Each channel corresponds to a band. Since all bands are observed at the same time for each exposure, PISCO's data can get rid of the fluctuation of the PSF and directly measure the wavelength dependence of the chromatic PSF shown in Figure 7.

Figure 8: Optical design of PISCO. The main light path is split into 4 channels corresponding to 4 bands in order to perform parallel observation. [16] (Credit: PISCO)

Second, the location of PISCO is very close to LSST (85 miles away), making it a suitable telescope for us to measure the chromatic PSF for LSST. The outer scale of the fluctuation model determines the chromatic effect of PSF, so, by studying the relationship between optical observation (PSF) and meteorological measurement (at PISCO), we can understand the variation of outer scale more deeply at the site of Las Campanas Observatory and use this result to infer the wavelength dependence at the LSST site.

PISCO has 4 bands, g,r,i,z. The efficiency of each band is plotted in Figure 9. Assume that the wavelength dependence is $PSF \propto \lambda^{-0.28}$. Taking the center value of wavelength, the difference of the PSFs between the g band and z band will be about 15%. This is about half a pixel for PISCO.

In this project, the image of each band is considered as one measurement on that band. And the wavelength of the measurement is calculated by getting the weighted average of the wavelength efficiency curve of each band. The center wavelength and uncertainty of all four bands are listed in Table 1.

4 Method

The data from PISCO we used is dated from June 9th, 2015 to June 22nd, 2017. Within the 14 observation days, 1124 exposures were taken, and our measurements of

Figure 9: Band efficiency plots of PISCO on g,r,i and z band (in the order of left to right)[16] (Credit: PISCO)

PSF were based on about 600,000 stars. We only took stars as samples to measure PSF because other extended objects had their intrinsic sizes, which made their FWHM significantly larger than those of the stars.

4.1 Image Processing

Before measuring the PSF of each star, we needed to process the raw data from PISCO. Each exposure came in eight channels. Channels 1 and 4 corresponded to the g-band, ranging from 400 nm to 550 nm. Channels 2 and 3 corresponded to the r-band, ranging from 550 nm to 700 nm. Channels 5 and 8 corresponded to the i-band, ranging from 700 nm to 850 nm. Channels 6 and 7 corresponded to the z-band, ranging from 820 nm to 1100 nm [16].

Table 1: Center values and their corresponding uncertainties of four bands in PISCO

Band name	Center wavelength (nm)	Uncertainty (nm)
g	489.3	60.7
r	620.4	68.8
i	758.5	82.0
z	876.2	66.9

After reorganizing the channels and trimming the images to exclude the dome, we cleaned defects in the images. This included CCD pixels blocked by dust (numerous pixels with values lower than 5 sigmas from the random noise), which were replaced with randomly generated values based on detected noise. Another defect was cosmic rays. We used *Lacosmic* from *ccdproc* [17] to eliminate cosmic rays in the images, as demonstrated in Figure 10.

We paid special attention to dust and cosmic rays to ensure precise background measurements, which are crucial for accurate FWHM measurements.

Figure 10: **Left:**Demonstration of dust and cosmic-rays in the images before the process,**Right:**After the process, dust and cosmic rays are gone

After we cleaned the image, we used a method from *photutils* to detect a 2D background for each exposure and subtract the local background from the image (an example is shown in Figure 11). When detecting the 2D background, all the stars were masked using the *SigmaClip* and *make_source_mask* methods in *photutils* [18].

Figure 11: Example of 2-D background estimation

4.2 Star Detection and Measuring PSF

After an image was processed, as described above, it was ready for the next stage of measurement. First, we detected the stars using the *DAOStarFinder* in *photutils* [19]. The method used a Gaussian kernel to fit the object in the exposure, and an object was considered valid if its peak was greater than 10 times the background noise. This threshold was chosen so that objects overlapping with each other would be excluded. One example of star detection is shown in Figure 12.

Figure 12: Example of star detection using *DAOStarFinder* on one of the images from PISCO[18]

For all the stars we found beforehand, we measured their FWHM by fitting the star with a circular Gaussian function plus a constant, and then obtained the

FWHM of the fitting function. The advantage of using the fitting to find the FWHM is that it eliminated the constant background on which the star was sitting.

Note that we excluded some of the stars that were overexposed by detecting their center ADC counts. If a star was overexposed, the measured PSF would be much larger than expected, as the Half-Maximum is underestimated because the center was cut.

4.3 Excluding Defocused Images

Since the effect was on the magnitude of a micrometer, a small amount of displacement of the CCD would result in a small blur for a point source. We tested the focus of the CCD by plotting the size of the PSF against each other, as shown in Figure 13. The PSFs of different bands should have been proportional to each other. If the plot did not pass through the origin, it meant that the image was defocused. An obviously defocused image would be excluded from the sample of measurements. However, subtle defocuses occurred in all of the images and were a cause of systematic error for the project.

Figure 13: **Up:** A Defocused Image **Down:** A well focused image. For some exposures with defocusing, we removed them from the data set.

For future studies to improve the quality of measurements, images would need to be deconvolved with the chromatic PSF of the telescope, and the CCD for each band would need to eliminate optical and electronic biases on the PSF measurements.

4.4 Data Reduction

Now that we had already measured all of the FWHM for the stars, how were we going to reduce the data and draw conclusions about the wavelength dependence of the PSF? We had two different approaches.

4.4.1 First Approach

The data flow of the first approach of data reduction is shown in Figure 14.

Figure 14: Flow of data reduction

The definition of one measurement of the PSF is the average FWHMs of all the detected stars in a single exposure, and the standard deviations for the stars in the star field, which were the errors of the measurements. The uncertainty of fitting the Gaussian kernel is negligible in this case since 98% of the stars had a fitting

uncertainty of less than 2%, but some of the differences between stars in the same exposure exceeded 200% (shown in Figure 15).

Figure 15: This plot shows that the relative uncertainty for PSF fitting is small enough to be ignored compared to the PSF difference between stars

After measuring the FWHM for the four bands of an exposure, we normalized the PSF by dividing all FWHMs by the FWHM value of the g band, so that they only revealed the relative scale compared to the g band. This is beneficial for calculating the power factor p , since it normalizes the absolute size factor a .

Then, we combined the FWHM averages for each band by calculating their weighted arithmetic mean. For example, for band k , the average PSF and its standard deviation were $PSF_{i,k}$ and $\sigma_{PSF_{i,k}}$ for $k \in [g, r, i, z]$, where the field number i stands for different exposures.

$$PSF_k = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^N (PSF_{i,k} \sigma_{PSF_{i,k}}^{-2})}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{PSF_{i,k}}^{-2}} \quad (7)$$

$$\sigma_k = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sum_{i=1}^N \sigma_{PSF_{i,k}}^{-2}}} \quad (8)$$

At last, by summarizing the FWHM measurements taken during 14 observation nights and 1124 starfields, we calculated the wavelength dependence of the PSF by fitting the average PSF for each band with $f(\lambda) = a\lambda^p$.

The major uncertainty of this measurement came from the fluctuation of the PSF over space and time. The fluctuation over time is canceled by the special property of simultaneous observation of PISCO; this is also the reason why we calculated the normalized PSF.

4.4.2 Second Approach

The second approach of data reduction deviates from the first approach after taking the average FWHMs of each band and each exposure. Instead of normalizing the average FWHMs by the value of the g band, we fit four values from the four bands with $f(\lambda) = a\lambda^p$, immediately resulting in N pairs of parameters for the fitting function with their uncertainty, where N is the number of exposures. We then made a histogram of the parameters and fit them with a Gaussian curve to determine the center value and the uncertainty of the power parameter p .

Another benefit of this approach was that we were observing the wavelength dependence exposure by exposure. So, we could directly compare the wavelength dependence with the parameters of that exposure, such as temperature, exposure time, etc., and determine if there were any correlations.

5 Results

In this section, we will first show the results of the wavelength dependence for our measurements on atmospheric PSF in both statistical approaches. After that, we will show the relationship of this dependence and other factors.

5.1 Wavelength Dependency of PSF

The wavelength dependence plot is shown in Figure 16, with the linear scale plot on the left and the logarithmic plot on the right. If we fit the result with the function $PSF = a \cdot \lambda^p$ (calculated the overall PSF for each band and fit to the four overall PSFs), we obtain the power factor $p = -0.25 \pm 0.03$. The prediction of the outer scale of LSST is about 25-50 meters, according to the simulation, and the

power index p is around -0.25 . However, the uncertainty of p is 0.03 , which means even the infinite outer scale is within 2 sigma of our measurement.

Figure 16: **Left:**PSF-Wavelength relationship in linear scale, **Right:**PSF-Wavelength relationship in logarithmic scale. Result: $p = -0.25 \pm 0.03$

We can also represent the power factor p in the other way, that is, fit the curve for each exposure and get the individual p factor, then plot the distribution of p to determine its center value and uncertainty, shown in Figure 17. In this way, the power factor p is measured as $p = -0.26 \pm 0.05$.

As mentioned before, the outer scale for LSST is 30 meters. If we assume that the Las Campanas Observatory has the same outer scale, the corresponding power

Figure 17: Distribution of power factor p over 1124 exposures Result: $p = -0.26 \pm 0.05$

factor will be about -0.25 according to Park’s simulation and -0.32 according to Gulshen’s calculation. This means our results deviate slightly from the simulation of the Von Karman Model. This might be caused by the optical or electronic chromatic effects of our instrumentation. The power factor p measured in our data is summarized in Table 2.

Data reduction method	power factor p	uncertainty
Average Then Fit	-0.25	0.03
Fit Then Average	-0.26	0.05

According to the theoretical chromatic PSF calculated by the Von Karman model in Figure 6, our power factor suggested that the outer scale of Las Campanas Observatory is in the range of 40 meters to over 100 meters according to Gulshen’s calculation and is centered around 25-50 meters according to Park’s simulation. The predicted outer scale of 30 meters is either very close to or lies within these ranges [10]. Since we only have four data points for wavelengths and our error bar of p is larger than its variation within the observation wavelength range, we did not try to fit the relationship of p and λ .

5.2 Relationship of the Dependence and Other Factors

In this section, we studied the correlation between the wavelength dependence of chromatic PSF and other factors. If there was a correlation between one and another, we could measure that dependence to further decrease the systematics of the PSF correction.

5.2.1 Power Factor p vs. FWHM

The measurement showed that the power factor p had almost no dependence on the width of the PSF, shown in Figure 18. This suggests that the size of the PSF and its chromatic effect are very weakly related, with a correlation of 0.02.

Figure 18: Relationship of power factor p and FWHM of PSF (correlation factor: 0.02), red line shows the linear fitting of our measurement, and the green line shows the plot according to simulation[6]

However, the simulation showed that a larger outer scale not only increased the power factor [6], but also increased the FWHM of the PSF. In our measurement, we only observed a weak correlation in this relationship that is not enough to verify the correlation observed in the simulation.

5.2.2 Power Factor and FWHM vs. Atmospheric and Telescope Parameters

One of the benefits of fitting the chromatic effect model for each exposure was that we could then try to study the relationship between the chromatic effect and

Figure 19: Power Factor and FWHM vs. Atmospheric Condition, from left to right, the factors are temperature, air pressure, humidity, and wind speed

the parameters for each exposure.

In Figure 19, the relationship between PSF width and atmospheric conditions, and between the power factor p and atmospheric conditions are plotted. We can see that a higher wind speed generally increased the absolute size of the PSF (Cor = 0.28). For the power factor p , it also had a weak negative correlation with temperature (Cor = -0.25) and wind speed (Cor = -0.3). This suggests that we should be aware of the wind speed and temperature when we choose the power factor p for the chromatic PSF model that we are going to use for correction.

We also measured the relationship between the chromatic PSF and the observational information: the exposure time, the airmass, and the elevation angle of the telescope, shown in Figure 20. As expected, a high airmass (Cor = 0.38) or a low elevation angle (Cor = -0.29) will cause the width of the PSF to increase, since the light travels through a heavier atmosphere for lower elevation angles. However, we also made sure that the p factor has no correlation with these factors.

Figure 20: Power Factor and FWHM vs. Telescope Parameters and Airmass, from left to right, the factors are exposure time, airmass and elevation degree

6 Discussion and Conclusion

6.1 Conclusion

In this project, we were able to measure the chromatic effect of the PSF using the raw data from PISCO. The results of the measurements generally agreed with previous calculations and simulations. These measurements provided convincing evidence that the PSF varies across different wavelengths and follows the Von Karman model. The measurements of the chromatic effect of the PSF will help sky survey researchers obtain a more realistic shape of galaxies by deconvolving the image with the chromatic PSF kernel described by this model. The results of our project are especially useful for LSST surveys since the sites we used were very close to LSST's site.

We suggest that the wavelength dependence of the atmospheric PSF, expressed by $FWHM(\lambda) = a\lambda^p$ where $p = -0.25 \pm 0.03$ or $p = -0.26 \pm 0.05$, depends on the statistical method we adopt. We also suggest that the outer scale at the site of LSST is centered around 25-50 meters, depending on which theoretical calculation we are applying. However, our measurement of the power factor had quite a large uncertainty; even the p for infinite outer scale was within the range of two sigma from our center value. Although the power factor p is also a function of wavelength according to the simulations, the differences of p within our observation wavelength range were less than 0.02, which is beyond our level of precision in these measurements.

In our measurements, we observed a very weak correlation between the absolute value of the FWHM and the power factor p . We failed to show the correlation predicted by the simulation.

We also found that the chromatic effect is affected by the wind speed and temperature of the sites, with the power factor p having correlation factors of -0.3 and -0.25, respectively. However, the air pressure, humidity, exposure time, and airmass do not affect the chromatic effect according to our measurements. This suggests that higher temperatures and faster wind speeds would decrease the outer scale of the eddies in the atmosphere.

6.2 Future Study

In future studies, this project can be improved in several aspects.

1. We did not consider the chromatic effects of the Magellan Telescope and

the CCD of PISCO. If the telescope, filter, or camera caused additional PSFs that also had wavelength dependence, we would need to study this effect further and deconvolve the image with this extra PSF.

2. Galaxy samples. The method we used to distinguish stars and galaxies was not the most sophisticated one. Any galaxy with a Gaussian profile was also included in our sample, and these galaxies would have a much larger FWHM since they are extended objects.

3. For a better measurement, one might consider using a star catalog to select the objects being measured. There are two advantages to doing this. First, it reduces the number of galaxies in the sample space. Second, we could normalize the PSF for each star, eliminating the spatial fluctuations of the PSF. It would have been even better if we had access to the spectrum of the stars, as this would allow us to better determine the center wavelength of the measurements by integrating the efficiency of the band multiplied by the SED.

In the end, I want to express my deep gratitude to my advisor, Professor Christopher Walter, for helping and guiding me throughout this thesis study. I also want to express my appreciation for all of the advice from my thesis committee, which significantly improved this project. I would like to thank everyone in the Duke Neutrino and Cosmology Group and those who helped me on this project. I also want to acknowledge the PISCO team for providing the excellent and unique dataset that made this project possible, especially Chris Stubbs, Brian Stalder, and Tony Stark. Josh Meyers from SLAC was also very helpful in undertaking this project.

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